

MILESTONES AND CHANGING CONTEXTS IN TEACHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS (TEIS) CALABARZON PHILIPPINES

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ABSTRACT

The changing contexts in the educational landscape have brought tremendous challenges and opportunities to Teacher Education Institutions. This study described the milestones of TEIs through its status also it delved into TEI's response to the changing contexts in its. The descriptive method of research was adapted through the use of a researcher – made questionnaire complemented by interviews and focus group discussion. Respondents were 130 faculty members and 31 academic leaders including the Deans, Associate Deans, Department and Programs chairpersons in TEIs. Weighted mean, frequency, percentage were utilized as statistical tools to treat gathered data. The findings revealed that in terms of the milestones of TEIs the enrolment and LET performance followed an increasing trend while they have varying accreditation levels. The TEIs are responsive of the changing contexts which includes the onset of various quality assurance undertakings, the observance the preparation and adaptability of both TEI's faculty and students of the PPST as a new standard for teachers' competencies and lastly implementation of a curriculum framework known as the Outcomes Based Education (OBE) as they were able to meet most of the challenges and opportunities. Lastly, the proposed comprehensive development program includes practicable activities that can be implemented by the academic leaders for them to adapt with challenges and opportunities brought by the changing contexts in TEIs.

Keywords: TEIs, Milestones in TEIs, Mixed Methodology, Changing Contexts